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LEADERSHIP STYLE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Education is the mirror of the society, showing its strength and weakness, hopes, biases and key values of its culture. Education has a definite role to play in the development of people and countries. The principal is the key person in the academic hierarchy of an institution. According to University Grant Commission, the principal is responsible for ensuring quality of education, administering admission, scheduling classes, determining the work load of teachers, faculty development, evaluation of campus programmes, students discipline, allocating finance within the limits set by the governing body, maintaining relations with the government, alumni, other support agencies and general public and overall coordination and management. The researcher has attempted to make a study on the leadership styles adopted by the school Principals of Kanniyakumari district. The sample taken for the study is 240 Principals from schools all over Kanniyakumari district. The objectives of the study was to understand the demographic profile of the school Principals and to analyse the leadership styles adopted by the school Principals. Drop off survey method and Mail survey method was used to collect the data. Simple Percentage analysis, Descriptive statistics in the form of Mean, Standard Deviation and One-way ANOVA was used to interpret the leadership styles.

Key words: Demographic , Leadership Styles, Relationship , School Principals

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the most important aspect of educational administration and management. The history of administration and management can be traced back as far as 1300 B.C., when the Egyptians were spreading their culture throughout the world. They had a system of large-scale administration. The Greeks introduced democracy into administration when it placed government in the hands of all men. It recognized such basic facts as: all men are equal before the law; a citizen should be interested not only in his own personal affairs, but also in the affairs of state; all citizens have a responsibility for deciding public policy; and full discussion of important public issues is an essential to good government. The Romans showed their ability in large-scale management, which included the administration of their own affairs as well as the affairs of their subjects. They established a paid system of civil service under Augustus about 25 B.C. Educational administrations is concerned with dealing and coordinating the activities of groups of people. It is the dynamic side of education. Educational philosophy sets the goal; educational psychology explains the principles of teaching and educational administration deals with the educational practices. It is planning, directing, controlling, executing and

evaluating the educative process. Current research has emphasized the significance of the concept, stating that effective schools should have leaders who articulate with the community.

LEADERSHIP STYLES

Leadership Style: involves three Leadership style; Autocratic Leadership, Democratic Leadership, and Laissez-faire Leadership. (Lewin, Lippit and White (1939) in the Leadership style experiments in 1939 identified the above three Leadership styles.

The first initiation in the field of leadership styles was in 1939. A group of researchers under the leadership of Kurt Lewin the famous psychologist conducted experiments on different styles of leadership. The experiments were conducted on specific group of school children and the researchers then observed the behavior of children in response to the different styles of leadership. Though recent researchers have identified more specific types of leadership, this early study was very influential and established three major leadership styles. They are Autocratic, Democratic and Laissez-fair. A brief description about these styles is given below:

Autocratic leadership

Where the leader exercises rigid control and believes in the carrot and stick method to motivate his subordinates. He prefers only one-way communication, i.e., top-down communication. There is one advantage here-the decision making takes less time, but this may antagonize the group members and adversely affect group morale. Autocratic leaders have the clear concept for what to be done, when it should be done, and how it should be done. He keeps the strong boundary between the leader and the followers. Autocratic leaders taking decisions independently without consulting the rest of the group. It is found that decision-making was less creative under Autocratic leadership.

Democratic leadership

According to Lewin's study democratic style of leadership is considered as the most effective leadership style. Here the leaders offer all helps to group members, and they themselves participating in the group. The leader believes in allowing participatory management and group members are free to give their opinion, decision-making is cooperative and members having a sense of belonging.

Laissez-fair leadership

Where the leader avoids contact with the group and there is a free climate and non-interference from the leader. Though the members have freedom, there is no control and group members may try to realize their personal objectives rather than group goals, with the result that group cohesiveness is lost ultimately. Lewin (1939) observed that Delegative leaders offer little or no guidance to group members and leave decision-making up to group members. While this style can be effective in situations where group members are highly qualified in an area of expertise, it often leads to poorly defined roles and a lack of motivation.

OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the demographic profile of the School Principals of Kanniyakumari district, namely age, gender and type of school.
2. To identify the relationship between the type of school and leadership style of school Principals in Kanniyakumari district

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pascale Hajal-Chibani (2016) has studied on leadership Styles of school principals. The author attempted to examine the leadership styles of school Principals The objectives of the study are 1. To examine leadership Styles of school principals as measured by Bolman and Deal (1991) after adapting it to the Lebanese context., and also compared the differences in leadership schools in the Lebanese context.It was found that there is differences in the leadership styles of the school Principals in Lebanon as measured by Bolman and Deal (1991) and the Principals consider themselves as effective leaders.

C.Subathra (2014) has studied the college Principals leadership Style, decision making Styles and motivation profile in Kanyakumari district. The study was conducted to examine the leadership Style, decision making Style and motivation profile of the college Principals in Kanyakumari district, to study the relationship between the leadership Style of college Principals in Kanyakumari district, to study the relationship between the decision making Style of college Principals in Kanyakumari district and their demographic profiles and to study the relationship between the Motivation profile of college Principals in Kanyakumari district and their demographic profiles.It was inferred in the study that here is no relationship between the leadership Styles of college Principals in Kanyakumari district and their age, the majority of college Principals in Kanyakumari district were females, the predominant leadership Style of the college Principals in Kanyakumari district was democratic leadership Style, most of the college Principals in Kanyakumari district had more than 25 years of teaching experience, th predominant motivation profile of the college Principals in Kanyakumari district was achievement motivation profile and there was no significant leadership between the Principals age and any of the factors of leadership behavior viz.leadership Style, decision making Style and motivation profile of the college Principals in Kanyakumari district.

Heba Alfahad,Dr. Salem Alhajri and Dr.Abdulmuhsen Alqahtani (2013) studied on the Relationship between school Principals Leadership Styles and Teachers Achievement Motivation. This paper examines the relationship between school Principals leadership Styles, whether transformational or transactional, on teachers achievement motivation. A total of 320 heads of Instructional departments were randomly selected from randomly selected Schools. The results revealed that a transformat leadership Style was prevalent among Principals and teachers achievement motivation was positive. There was a positive correlation between the Principals transformational leadership Style and the teachers achievement motivation.

Sushil Kumar Dubey (2012) had conducted a study to measure the leadership of Principals of secondary Schools of Saurashtra region of Gujarat with respect to their different group of variables of this study, to compare the difference between the leadership of Principals of secondary Schools with respect to their demographics viz., Gender, Educational Qualification,

Social category, Type of school management, Working experience, Residing Area. The data clearly implied that the style of the Principal needs to be improved, the data indicates that ownership does moderate the difference between leadership Styles.

Ninama K.C. (2011) studied the leadership style of Primary school Principals in Bhiloda Taluka of Sabarkantha District. The investigation was to study the work style habit of the Principals. From the population of 120 teachers 30 Principals from 30 Schools were taken as sample of Bhiloda Taluka of Sabarkantha district. Self made tool was taken. Survey type method was followed. From the analysis it was found that most of the primary schools Principals were co-operative with all the teachers and their work habits were less effective. Their decision making power was good and they were all able to take right and quick decision but the power was in the hands of superior officers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- The present research is designed to study on the problem “Leadership Style, and the Profile of School Principals’ in Kanyakumari District”.
- The researcher used survey method (50% through Drop-off Survey and 50% through Mail survey) which is considered appropriate method of obtaining specific data about the research situation. As a research technique in the social sciences, Management and Commerce survey research has considerable credibility, demonstrated by its widespread acceptance and use in academic institutions. Survey research involves soliciting self-reported verbal information from people. The ultimate goal of survey research is to allow researchers to generalize about a large population by studying only a small portion of the population. The surveys allowed researcher to obtain data about the Leadership styles of the School Principals in Kanyakumari District.
- **Simple Percentage Analysis** has been used to analyse the demographic profile of the School Principals of Kanyakumari district.
- Descriptive analysis and One-Way ANOVA was applied to describe the various leadership styles of the School Principals and to find the relationship between the leadership styles and type of school.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Demographic Profile of School Principals

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the School Principals

Age of the Principals		
AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
BELOW 40	18	7.53
41-45	30	12.5
46-50	58	24.2
51-55	62	25.8
56 & ABOVE	72	30

TOTAL	240	100.0
Gender of the Principals		
GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MALE	94	39.2
FEMALE	146	60.8
TOTAL	240	100.0
Type of School of the Principal		
TYPE OF SCHOOL	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
NURSERY & PRIMARY	44	18.3
PRIMARY ONLY	57	23.8
HIGHER SECONDARY	39	16.3
HIGH SCHOOL	37	15.4
MIDDLE SCHOOL	63	26.2
TOTAL	240	100.0

Source: Primary data

It was found that the minimum age of the respondents was 38, the maximum age was 60, and the mean was Table 1 shows age group wise frequency and percentage of the respondent, in that most respondents were in the age range of 51-55, followed by the age range of 46-50. The majority 60.8% of the principals were female, compared with 39.2% male Principals. Most respondents were from middle school n=63 (26.2%) followed by primary schools only n= 57 (23.8%).

Table 2. Leadership Style of the respondent (Frequency and Percentage)

	VERY LOW RANGE	LOW RANGE	MODE RATE RANGE	HIGH RANGE	VERY HIGH RANGE	TOTAL
AUTOCRATIC	n 35 (14.6%)	n 35 (14.6%)	n 42 (17.5%)	n 52 (21.7%)	n 76 (31.6%)	240 (100%)
DEMOCRATIC	n 41 (17.0%)	n 22 (9.2%)	n 33 (13.8%)	n 65 (27.0%)	n 79 (33.0%)	240 (100%)

LAISSEZ-FAIRE	n 66 (27.5%)	n 48 (20.0%)	n 28 (11.7%)	n 44 (18.3%)	n 54 (22.5%)	240 (100%)
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Source: Primary data

Fig 1. Leadership Style of the respondent (Frequency and Percentage)

Frequency and percentage of the respondents Leadership style is shown in the above table It shows that the majority of the respondents 33.0% (n= 79) scored very high range level of intensity for the Democratic leadership style followed by 31.6% (n= 76) in Autocratic leadership style. It also shows that 27.5% (n= 66) scored high range level of intensity for the democratic leadership style followed by Autocratic Leadership style. That means the majority of respondents scored within high range and very high range for the Democratic leadership style.

Table – 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of the Leadership Styles Scale

SCALE	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
AUTOCRATIC	240	3.52	1.454
DEMOCRATIC	240	3.60	1.479

LAIZZES-FAIRE	240	2.98	1.565
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Source: Primary data

The result of the study reveals that the score of the Autocratic leadership is 3.52. The range of this style is between 1 to 5. And 3 is the midpoint, 5 is the highest possible score. The Standard Deviation is 1.454. The score of Democratic leadership is 3.60. The range of this style is also between 1 to 5. And 3 is the midpoint, 5 is the highest possible score. The Standard Deviation is 1.479. The score of Laizzes-faire leadership is 2.98. The range of this style is also between 1 to 5. And 3 is the midpoint, 5 is the highest possible score. The Standard Deviation is 1.565. Thus, the result proves that the Democratic styles are predominant among the principal of Kanyakumari District.

CONCLUSION

In the present study the investigator considered Lewin's basic style theory to identify the existing leadership styles. When compare to other areas of leadership especially in industrial, military etc. education field is lagging behind in adapting new trends and methods in administration and management. Hence, in the present study, the investigator mainly intended to assess the existing condition of the school principals in Kanyakumari District. Considering the above mentioned conditions of the school principals, the researcher strongly believe that it is better to consider Lewin's basic leadership style theory and the result proves that the Democratic styles are predominant among the principal of Kanyakumari District backed by Autocratic style.

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